

A Review paper On Thermal Performance Enhancement of Pulsating Heat Pipes Using Nanofluids

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Abstract—The advancement of modern technology has significantly increased the demand for compact and efficient thermal management systems, particularly in the field of electronic device cooling. Among the various solutions, heat pipes integrated with mono and hybrid nanofluids have gained attention for their potential to enhance heat transfer and support system miniaturization. This report delivers a comprehensive review of recent developments in pulsating heat pipe (PHP) technology. It begins with a foundational introduction to heat pipes, followed by an in-depth discussion on different wick structures, including sintered, grooved, and mesh designs. The study further investigates the role of mono and hybrid nanofluids as working fluids and highlights their applications. Research conducted over the last decade is reviewed, focusing on the classification of heat pipes, the selection of working fluids, methods for preparing nanofluids, and the techniques used for their characterization. The influence of various operational parameters such as the size, shape, and concentration of nanoparticles, filling ratio, thermal conductivity, and heat input is thoroughly examined.

Keywords — Pulsating Heat Pipe (PHP), Nanofluids, Thermal Management, Electronic Cooling, Heat Transfer Enhancement

I. INTRODUCTION

With the ongoing advancements in electronic technologies, the increasing power density and heat flux have posed significant challenges in maintaining optimal operating temperatures of components. The trend toward miniaturization further intensifies the need for highly efficient and compact thermal management systems. Effective dissipation of heat is essential to ensure reliability and longevity in various electronic devices such as CPUs, LEDs, rectifiers, thyristors, transistors, RF amplifiers, and high-density semiconductors. To address these thermal issues, extensive research over the past decade has focused on optimizing heat transfer devices, particularly heat pipes. These passive systems use the latent heat of vaporization of working fluids to transfer thermal energy efficiently over a distance. Studies have explored a wide range of configurations, including cylindrical, flat, rotating, loop, and pulsating heat pipes, each tailored to specific applications. In recent years, nanofluids base fluids containing suspended nanoparticles have been introduced into heat pipe systems to further enhance thermal performance. The efficiency of such systems depends on multiple factors, including the type and structure of the heat pipe, characteristics of the working fluid, nanoparticle properties (such as size, shape, and concentration), and operating conditions.

This report provides a comprehensive review of nanofluid-based heat pipe technologies, with a special focus on pulsating heat pipes (PHPs) due to their superior thermal behaviour and structural simplicity. The study also discusses preparation and characterization methods, performance variables, and identifies current challenges along with future research opportunities in this evolving field.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Noise et al. (2009) [1] experimentally, studied the heat transfer enhancement in two phases closed thermosyphon using $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{water}$. 1000 mm long copper pipe was used as container material. Al_2O_3 nanoparticles were dispersed in distillate water by ultrasonication without using dispersed for 1–3 v% concentration. Outcomes- Efficiency was increased up to 14.7% as compared with pure water. Han et al. (2011) [2] Types of Nano fluids: $\text{Ag-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Water}$ % concentration: 0.005–0.05 v% Particle size (nm): 27, 89 and selected parameters for evaluation. Orientation (Deg.): 5, 45, 90 Heat Load (W): 50–300 W (dW $\frac{1}{4}$ 50W). Outcomes- Use of mono and hybrid nanofluids leads to worse thermal performance Liu et al. (2011) [3] Types of

Nano fluids: Cu, CuO, SiO₂/water % concentration: 0.5, 1.0, 1.2 wt% Particle size (nm): 20, 30, 40, 50 Description Of operating parameters: Heat Load (W): 0–70 Surface temperature (C): 40, 50,60 Pressure: 7.45, 12.38, 19.97 kPa. Outcomes- Smaller size nano particles had better heat transfer rate as compare to larger size. Huminic et al. (2011) [4] experimental studied the thermal performance of thermosyphon heat pipe using iron oxide/DI water nanofluid. Nanofluids were prepared by one step method. XRD and HRTEM (High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy) technique were used for characterization. Huminic et al. [4]. Types of NFs: Iron oxide/DI Water, %concentration: 2.0, 5.3 %, Particle size (nm): 4-5. Outcomes- Thermal resistance of Thermosyphon with iron oxide nanofluid had lower than DI water. Kamyar et al. (2013) [5] experimentally, studied the effects of Al₂O₃/DI water and TiSiO₄/DI water nanofluids on heat transfer characteristics of a two-phase closed thermosyphon. Nanofluids were prepared by two step method using ultrasonic homogenizer at 50 kHz sound frequency. TEM technique was used for characterization of both nanofluids. Types of nanofluids: Ag/water % concentration: 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 w % Filling ratio: 30, 40, 80 % Heat Load: 0–4 kW/m² Surface temperature (°C): 60, 70, 80. Outcomes-Highest heat flux of 25 kW/m² and highest effectiveness of 0.3 were achieved at 50 % filling ratio and 1 wt% concentration. Liu et al. (2013) [6] experimentally, studied the thermal performance of an open thermosyphon using CuO/DI water nanofluid for evacuated tubular high temperature air solar collector. Nanofluid was prepared by direct dispersing CuO particles in base fluid and then oscillated continuously for about 10 hours in ultrasonic bath with working frequency of 25–40kHz. SEM technique was used to analyse the nanoparticle suspension in nanofluid. Particle size (nm): 13, 50 Types of nanofluids: CuO/DI Water % concentration: 0.8–1.5 wt% Filling ratio: 60%. Particle size (nm): 20-50, Pressure: -0.9 bar, Heat Load (W): 300- 1200 Surface temperature (°C): 0°-40° Outcomes- air outlet temperature and system collecting efficiency of the solar air collector using nanofluid was higher than water. Huminic et al. (2013) [7] experimentally and numerically, studied the heat transfer characteristics of thermosyphon heat pipe using Fe₂O₃/water nanofluid. Nanofluid was prepared by two step method. XRD, SaED and HRTEM techniques were performed for characterization. Types of nanofluids: Fe₂O₃/water % concentration: 2, 5.3 v% Particle size (nm): 4-5, Orientation (Deg.): 60, 70, 80, 90 Heat Load (W): 60, 70, 80, 90 Surface temperature (C): 60-90, Nanofluids (NFs) are generally suspensions of metal or metal oxide particles/fibres with an average size of about 1-100 nm. Common nanoparticles (NPs) include Al₂O₃, TiO₂, CuO, Au, Ag and Si, which may be added to aqueous or alcohol base fluids, and are synthesized in a number of ways, such as by inert gas condensation (Granqvist & Buhrman, 1976), chemical vapor deposition (Choi et al., 2001), spray-drying (Ashley, 1994), and rapid expansion in supersonic nozzles (Hill et al., 1963). Ultrasonic agitation and additional surfactants are also used to promote better uniformity and to prevent agglomeration of nanoparticles in solution (Lee et al. 1999). The feasibility and effectiveness of thermal enhancement of fluids with nanoparticles (and the term “nanofluid”) was introduced by Choi & Eastman (1995). Prior to the theoretical work of Choi & Eastman (1995), it was largely understood that the effective conductivity of a solution could be enhanced by addition of supplemental high-conductivity particles. In fact, Maxwell (1881) theoretically modelled the effective thermal conductivity of suspensions containing spherical particles. However, most studies focused on the addition of micro-scale particles, which showed limited use in practical engineering applications because of clogging problems (Choi & Tran 1991; Choi et al., 1992a, 1992b). In stationary fluids, nanofluids have demonstrated relatively high temperature-dependent effective thermal conductivities (Eastman et al., 2001; Choi et al., 2001; You et al., 2003) that exceed those of traditional solid-liquid suspensions. Eastman et al. (2001) observed an increase in effective conductivity of about 40% using 0.3 vol.% metallic copper nanoparticles as compared to the base fluid of ethylene glycol. Choi et al. (2001) similarly saw an increase in effective thermal conductivity for a dispersion of carbon nanotubes in a synthetic poly (α -olefin) oil; however, it was noted that the increase in effective thermal conductivity was non-linear, and was not accurately predicted using previous models, including those of Maxwell (1881) and the Hamilton & Crosser (1959) model. Nanofluid behaviour and enhancement has also been investigated for various convective and phase-change applications. You et al. (2003) experimentally studied the thermal behaviour of aqueous Al₂O₃ nanofluids for pool boiling at different nanoparticle concentrations. The experiment indicated a ~200% increase in the critical heat flux compared to that for the pure water case (though the nucleate boiling heat transfer coefficients appeared to be equal for both cases). Putra et al. (2003) studied natural convective heat transfer of a 4.0% Al₂O₃ nanofluid inside a horizontal cylinder that was heated and cooled at opposite ends. However, it was found that the convective heat transfer coefficient for nanoparticle solutions was less than that for the same system charged with distilled water. Putra et al. (2003) concluded that the heat transfer 3 deterioration ultimately depended on particle density, concentration, as well as the aspect ratio of the outer cylinder. Xuan & Li (2000) summarized a procedure for preparation of a homogenous nanofluid solution, along with a theoretical model to predict the heat transfer of turbulent nanofluid flow in a tube. A dispersed model was used to account for the complex one- and multi-dimensional interactions of Brownian diffusion, sedimentation, and dispersion which coexist in nanofluid convective flows. Heat pipes and gravity-assisted thermosyphons are effective, passive devices that enable high rates of heat transfer using internal phase change mechanisms (Faghri 2012, 2014, 2016; Shabgard et al. 2015). a conventional heat pipe is typically a rigid, sealed container under vacuum, charged with an amount of liquid. a heat source is applied to the evaporator, and heat is transferred to the wick structure by a combination of conduction and convection. The liquid contained in the wick structure vaporizes and passes to the evacuated vapor core of the heat pipe. The vapour then moves through the adiabatic section, which provides near-isothermal internal heat transfer at steady-state conditions. The vapor undergoes condensation in the condenser section, which is cooled by an external heat sink. The liquid condensate is then pumped back to the evaporator section via capillary action, where it again undergoes

evaporation. The latent heat transfer from vaporization and condensation in the evaporator and condenser sections, respectively, allow for the high heat transfer rates and minimal thermal resistance of heat pipes. Thermosyphons operate similarly to heat pipes, but do not rely on a wick structure for recirculation of the condensate; instead, they rely on gravity assisted-condensate films to continue the internal wetting of the evaporator section. The performances of various nanofluids are evaluated with respect to nanoparticle concentration and overall thermal conductivity of the nanofluid-charged heat pipes. Thermal conductivity enhancement versus Al_2O_3 nanoparticle concentration. Outcomes-Experimental and numerical results showed better heat transfer characteristics of thermosyphon using nanofluid as compared with water. Menlik et al. (2015) [8] experimentally, investigated the thermosyphon type heat pipe using MgO/water nanofluids. One step method was used for nanofluids preparation. Types of nanofluids: MgO/Water % concentration: 1–5 v% Filling ratio: 33.3% HP Particle size (nm): 40, Types of nanofluids: MgO/Water % concentration: 1–5 v% Filling ratio: 33.3% HP Particle size (nm): 40. Outcomes- Heat transfer rate was enhanced by 26% at 200 W heating power and 7.5 g/s flow rate. Latibari et al. (2016) [9] experimentally, investigated the effect of aqueous nitrogen doped graphene nanofluid on thermal performance of grooved copper heat pipe. Nanofluid was prepared using one step method. FESEM (Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy) technique was used for characterization. Types of nanofluids: NDG/Water % concentration: 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06 wt%, Orientation (Deg.): 0–90 Heat Load (W): 0–120 W Surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$): 15–40, Pressure: 1 kPa. Outcomes- Thermal resistance was decrease by 58.6 % and heat transfer coefficient was enhanced by 99% at 0.06 wt% concentration, 90 inclination angle and 120 W heat loads. Yang et al. (2019) [10] In the present work, an experimental investigation was conducted to quantify the heat transfer coefficient, thermal resistance and the thermal performance of a thermosyphon heat pipe charged with zirconia-acetone nanofluid. The thermosyphon was designed to operate at high heat fluxes such as 200 kW/m^2 similar or larger than the evacuated solar tube heat pipes. The zirconia-acetone nanofluid was prepared and stabilized by adding a surfactant, homogenizing with sonication and setting the pH of the nanofluid with a buffer solution. The thermosyphon was fabricated with an oxygen-free copper with the internal and outer diameters of 10.7 mm and 12 mm, respectively and the axial length of 280 mm. The thermal performance of the heat pipe was assessed for various heat fluxes (1 kW/m^2 –200 kW/m^2), filling ratio (20%–75%), tilt angle (5° – 70°) and the mass fraction of the nanofluid (0.025%–0.1%). Results showed that the presence of the nanofluid decreases the total thermal resistance of the heat pipe reaching the minimum value at the largest heat flux applied to the evaporator. also, the heat transfer coefficient of the evaporator was increased. Likewise, the zirconia-acetone nanofluid enhanced the boiling heat transfer mechanism and the geyser boiling, which resulted in the enhancement in the thermal performance of the heat pipe due to the increase in the heat transfer coefficient of the heat pipe by 36.3% at wt. % = 0.1 in comparison with the pure acetone. The optimum tilt angle and filling ratio values were 65° and 60%, respectively, in which the highest heat transfer coefficient was achieved. a correlation was also developed using a dimensionless analysis to predict the Kutateladze number as an index for the thermal performance of the heat pipe. Types of nanofluids: ammonia, R-134a, filling ratio: 50%, Orientation (Deg.):50,60 Heat Load (W): 440 W to 821 W, Operating Temp. temp.(C): -10 to 45° . Outcomes- Effectiveness of cooling was more than 30% increased. The best performance occurred at the installation angle of 60 and the recovery effectiveness reached about 50%. Wook young Kim al. (2020) [11] Types of NFs: Silicon/Ethanol, R-134a diameter of 923 μm , filing ratio :50%, Inclination angle ($^{\circ}$): 90° Heat Load (W): 40 W to 80 W. Outcomes-The CLPHP has 72% lower thermal resistance and 117% higher maximum allowable heat flux than the CEPHP. Mameli et al. (2020) [12] Types of Nano fluids: $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Ethanol}$ filling ratio: 50%, Orientation (Deg.):45,70 Heat Load (W): 200 W to 300 W, Operating Temp (C): -10 to 45° . The thermal characterization of a hybrid TS/PHP prototype under a varying gravity field is presented here to prove the feasibility of a future experiment onboard the International Space Station. The device is equipped with temperature and pressure sensors as well as with a transparent sapphire insert for the simultaneous high-speed imaging acquisition. The main research outcomes are listed below: In comparison with a previous experiment with a smaller number of heated sections, the absence of stop-over periods is beneficial in terms of heat transfer rate. Indeed, for the same wall-to-fluid heat input flux, the temperature difference at the evaporator between the beginning and the end of the microgravity periods is always smaller with the present PHP. Novel starts up tests, where the heat load is provided after the occurrence of microgravity, show that the 20 s microgravity period is enough for the device activation device and that, most important, prove that the PHP operation is not primed by the flow inertial effect, still present when the device is activated before the microgravity period. • The different kind of local thermodynamic states in the PHP have been discussed. a technique for the simultaneous measurement of the fluid pressure and temperature has been successfully implemented on a hybrid TS/PHP and tested in microgravity conditions showing the existence of subcooled and superheated local thermodynamic states. In the present case the evaporator is mainly superheated and the condenser is mainly subcooled but the subcooling level and time percentage increase with the heat input level. The difference between the actual fluid temperature and the corresponding saturated temperature records peaks from -5 K to $+2\text{ K}$ when a stable circulation was achieved before microgravity. Further work to detect the local fluid phase in the measurement location is needed to distinguish stable and metastable states. Outcomes- Overall heat transfer improved and best stability of mixture. Zufar al. (2020) [13] This study investigates the thermal performance of a four-turns Pulsating Heat Pipe (PHP) using a weight concentration of 0.1 wt% Al_2O_3 -CuO hybrid nanofluid, 0.1 wt% SiO_2 -CuO hybrid nanofluid and water both experimentally and numerically. The start-up pulsations, average evaporator temperatures, thermal resistance, two-phase flow, and non-linear temperature analysis were evaluated with respect to heating power and filling ratio of 10–100 W and 50–60%,

respectively. Stability measurement and characterization of thermal conductivity and viscosity properties of hybrid nanofluids were determined. From the experimental results, the thermal resistance SiO₂-CuO hybrid nanofluid exhibited was the lowest, i.e. 57% lower than that of water, followed by the Al₂O₃-CuO hybrid nanofluid, i.e. 34% lower than that of water at the heat input and filling ratio of 80 W and 60%, respectively. Nevertheless, the thermal conductivity and viscosity of Al₂O₃-CuO hybrid nanofluid were higher than those of SiO₂-CuO hybrid nanofluid. The increased viscosity found in Al₂O₃-CuO hybrid nanofluid would hinder the fluid transportation in PHP, thus augmenting the thermal resistance. Meanwhile, the hybrid nanofluids were able to achieve start-up pulsations earlier and they required lower heating power to reach start-up pulsations as compared to water. At low heating power (below 30 W), the differences in average evaporator temperatures for hybrid nanofluids and water were very small. However, at higher heating power (above 30 W), the differences were significant. The numerical results compared well with that earlier experimental work, thus indicating the reliability of the current numerical simulation. Types of NFs: Al₂O₃-CuO/Ethanol, Filling ratio :50–60%, Inclination angle (°):90, Heat Load (W):10–100 W. Outcomes- Thermal conductivity of Al₂O₃-CuO hybrid nanofluid were seen to enhance by up to 15% compared to water at 80 C. Kavusi et al. (2020) [14] experimental investigation was performed on the thermal performance and heat transfer characteristics of acetone/zirconia nanofluid in a straight (rod) gravity-assisted heat pipe. The heat pipe was fabricated from copper with a diameter of 15 mm, evaporator-condenser length of 100 mm and adiabatic length of 50 mm. The zirconia-acetone nanofluid was prepared at 0.05–0.15% wt. Influence of heat flux applied to the evaporator, filling ratio, tilt angle and mass concentration of nanofluid on the heat transfer coefficient of heat pipe was investigated. Results showed that the use of nanofluid increases the heat transfer coefficient while decreasing the thermal resistance of the heat pipe. However, for the filling ratio and tilt angle values, the heat transfer coefficient initially increases with an increase in both. However, from a specific value, which was 0.65 for filling ratio and 60–65 deg for tilt angle, the heat transfer coefficient was suppressed. This was attributed to the limitation in the internal space of the heat pipe and also the accumulation of working fluid inside the bottom of the heat pipe due to the large tilt angle. Overall, zirconia-acetone showed a great potential to increase the thermal performance of the heat pipe. Dependence of heat transfer coefficient of evaporator on the filling ratio of the working fluid and for various mass concentrations of nanofluids. Outcomes-Thermal efficiency was enhanced by 10.60% by using 0.10v% concentration. Optimum angles were 60° and 45° for DI water and alcohol respectively. Kim et al. (2016) [16] Types of nano fluids: Graphene Oxide/water % concentration: 0.01, 0.03 v, Heat Load (W): 25–450, Surface temperature (C): 0–140, Pressure: 14.5 kPa. Outcomes-Thermal resistance was decreased by 25%. 0.03 v% concentration showed lower heat transfer than 0.01 v%. Vijaykumar et al. (2017) [17] Types of nano fluids: CuO, Al₂O₃/DI Water % concentration: 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 wt % Particle size (nm): 20, 50, Orientation (Deg.): 0-90 Heat Load (W): 30-150 Surface temperature (C): 0-30. Outcomes-Max. thermal efficiency of Heat pipe filled with CuO was 30.42 % at 1.0 wt% concentration and Al₂O₃ was 26.17 % at 1.5 wt% concentration.

Fig. 1. The Number of paper's published between 2009 and 2018[18]

III. RESEARCH GAP

The reviewed literature highlights significant advancements in enhancing heat transfer performance using nanofluid-based thermosyphons and heat pipes; however, several research gaps remain. Despite the exploration of various nanoparticles and base fluids, the optimization of hybrid nanofluids in terms of composition, thermal conductivity, and long-term stability is underexplored. Most studies lack long-duration testing, leading to limited understanding of particle agglomeration, sedimentation, and performance degradation over time. Additionally, experiments are largely constrained to low-to-moderate heat fluxes and narrow temperature ranges, limiting applicability in high-performance scenarios like aerospace or solar thermal systems. The absence of a standardized evaluation framework across studies hinders meaningful performance comparisons, while the use of working fluids remains focused primarily on DI water and ethanol, with minimal investigation into refrigerants or cryogenic fluids. Advanced diagnostic tools, such as flow visualization and real-time monitoring, are seldom employed, restricting insights into internal flow behaviour and phase-change dynamics. Geometrical and orientation influences are partially studied, with scarce data on grooved or wick-structured systems. Numerical models often lack sufficient experimental validation and fail to capture the complexities of nanofluid behaviour under phase-change conditions. Furthermore, research on gravity and orientation effects in microgravity environments is limited, despite its relevance for space applications. Lastly,

environmental impacts, economic feasibility, and lifecycle assessments of nanofluids are rarely addressed, presenting a critical gap for real-world implementation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The following major conclusions are drawn from the review of literature on the application of nanofluid-based thermosyphons and heat pipes for heat transfer enhancement:

- The thermal performance of heat pipes can be significantly improved using oxide-based nanofluids, particularly those containing aluminium and copper nanoparticles. These materials offer high potential for enhancement while remaining cost-effective.
- An optimal nanoparticle concentration of 1.0 wt% ensures stable and efficient thermal behaviour.
- A filling ratio of 50% based on the volume of the evaporator section is considered ideal for achieving optimal thermal performance in heat pipes.
- The improved thermal performance of nanofluid-based heat pipes can be attributed to several mechanisms: (i) The presence of suspended nanoparticles promotes the formation of vapor bubbles, increasing their quantity while decreasing their size, thereby enhancing heat transfer in the evaporator region. (ii) Nanoparticles boost the thermophysical properties of the working fluid, such as thermal conductivity. (iii) The deposition of nanoparticles on the inner pipe walls forms a porous, artificial layer, which increases the effective heat transfer area and improves both the heat transfer coefficient and heat flux.
- Significant enhancement in thermal conductivity is achievable only through the use of hybrid nanofluids rather than single-component (mono) nanofluids.
- The primary objective of utilizing hybrid nanoparticle-based fluids is to leverage the synergistic effects that result in enhanced heat transfer rates and improved stability, while also reducing fluid viscosity. However, further theoretical and experimental studies are essential to thoroughly understand the thermal behaviour of heat pipes using different nanoparticle concentrations, types of heat pipes, working fluids, hybrid fluid compositions, inclination angles, filling ratios, heat inputs, and temperature ranges.

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